

The role of pesticides and fertilizers in Czech cereal output and TFP growth: A flexible production function with endogenous inputs

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ABSTRACT

Through a comprehensive analysis of the effects of fertilizers and pesticides on both output and total factor productivity (TFP) growth, this study contributes to the discussion on the impacts of agrochemical use in sustainable cereal production systems. Using FADN data from Czech cereal farmers from 2008 to 2020, the study employs a flexible translog (TL) production function alongside a proxy-variable approach that treats pesticides and fertilizers as endogenous inputs. This approach generates robust results that strengthen the evidence base essential for data-driven agricultural policy formulation. The findings highlight the critical role of fertilizers and pesticides as key inputs driving both output and TFP growth. Simulations suggest that reducing these inputs would lead to a decline in agricultural output; however, this outcome is not inevitable. The study finds that technological advancements, which also serve as important drivers of both output and TFP growth, can mitigate potential declines in agricultural output, ensuring a more sustainable transition.

1. Introduction

The effort to make Europe a climate-neutral continent by 2050 under the Green Deal (European Commission, 2020a) places significant pressure on the agricultural sector. At the heart of the Green Deal, the Farm-to-Fork Strategy aims to establish a European food system that ensures food security, nutrition, and public health while reducing its environmental and climate footprint. To achieve a neutral or positive environmental impact within the food system, the strategy calls for reducing the dependence of Europe's agriculture sector on pesticides and fertilizers. Specifically, it sets ambitious targets: a reduction of at least 20% in fertilizer use, a 50% reduction in chemical pesticide use (compared to 1990 levels), and an increase in the share of agricultural land under organic farming to 25% by 2030 (European Commission, 2020b). However, pesticides and fertilizers have historically been considered essential for increasing agricultural productivity, protecting crops, and maximizing yields (Dobrin et al., 2022). Therefore, ensuring a sufficient supply of affordable food with minimal environmental impacts requires transforming agricultural practices to enhance sustainability. At the farm level, decision-makers face the challenge of compensating for the loss of their systems' full production potential by integrating new environmentally friendly technologies within a relatively short timeframe. This decision directly impacts both the profitability and

competitiveness of agricultural producers (Beckman et al., 2020). Agricultural policy should incentivize farmers to adopt these sustainable practices (Cortignani et al., 2022). However, effective policy design requires an understanding of the extent to which productivity growth is driven by inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides, as well as the role of technological change (TC) (O'Donnell, 2010).

Several studies have examined the economic implications of reducing agrochemical inputs, particularly under the Farm-to-Fork strategy, employing general or partial equilibrium models (Beckman et al., 2020; Bremmer et al., 2021) or an agro-economic model (Cortignani et al., 2022). Wesseler (2022) highlighted that a reduction in crop yields leads to a significant decline in European agricultural production, higher food prices, and an overall loss in net welfare. Potential solutions include adopting new technologies to improve resource efficiency, such as precision farming—specifically precision fertilization (Heyl et al., 2023)—and applying modern biotechnologies (Noleppa and Carlsburg, 2021). Additionally, reallocating resources to areas where productivity remains low and has not yet reached its full potential, even in organic agriculture, can be beneficial (Wesseler, 2022). A common theme among these solutions is an emphasis on productivity growth.

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The economic literature distinguishes between two key concepts of productivity: partial factor productivity (PFP) and total factor productivity (TFP). PFP provides readily available information for understanding the underlying factors driving productivity changes; however, its results can be misleading since it does not account for all production inputs. Moreover, PFP may be higher for some inputs than others, making productivity comparisons between farms or across time difficult. In contrast, TFP offers a comprehensive measure of total productivity change by comparing the aggregate volume of outputs to the aggregate volume of inputs used in production (Wang et al., 2020; Murray, 2016). According to Comin (2010), TFP represents “the portion of output not explained by the amount of inputs used in production”, with its growth measured by the Solow (1957) residual. Productivity growth, defined in this way, is considered a non-structural concept (Gong and Sickles, 2020). Empirical analysis of TFP typically employs either a parametric approach, such as the Stochastic Frontier Approach (SFA), or a non-parametric approach, such as the Data Envelopment Approach (DEA). These help approximate frontier technology and isolate the effects of inefficient behavior from other sources of productivity gains, including technological change, economies of scale, and shifts in input–output composition (Balk et al., 2020).

Since frontier function estimates may suffer from input endogeneity—where efficiency and productivity levels are known to decision makers when determining input use but remain unobservable to economists—a behavioral framework was incorporated into the estimation of production technology, making it a structural approach to productivity analysis (Gong and Sickles, 2020). This approach enables the measurement of productivity growth within an input-specific framework, distinguishing between variable and quasi-fixed inputs. While the quasi-fixed inputs, such as capital, are predetermined, the use of variable inputs is influenced by short-run productivity changes. This responsiveness of input choice to productivity shocks introduces simultaneity issues in the modeling of the production process, particularly for inputs that can be adjusted in the short term, such as fertilizers and pesticides (Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003).

To address the simultaneity problem, which can lead to biased parameter and productivity estimates, Olley and Pakes (1996) and Levinsohn and Petrin (2003) proposed a proxy variable approach, in which a proxy derived from a structural model is used to control the error component associated with productivity. While Olley and Pakes (1996) used investment as a proxy for unobserved productivity shocks, Levinsohn and Petrin (2003) instead employed an intermediate input such as materials and/or energy. The literature suggests that intermediate inputs offer several advantages over investment proxies in estimating production functions. Specifically, they mitigate issues related to lumpy investment data, such as the truncation of firms reporting zero investment. Additionally, intermediate inputs can more accurately capture firms’ responses to productivity shocks due to their lower adjustment costs, thereby providing a more precise proxy and a stronger connection between estimation strategies and economic theory.

Ackerberg et al. (2015) provided a detailed comparison of the methodologies developed by Olley and Pakes (1996) and Levinsohn and Petrin (2003), noting that these techniques may suffer from a functional dependence problem. To address this issue, they proposed an alternative approach based on a conditional input demand function, rather than the unconditional function used in the Olley and Pakes and Levinsohn and Petrin methods. More recently, Kumbhakar and Li (2024) applied this proxy variable approach to estimate a production function incorporating both variable and quasi-fixed inputs, thereby addressing the endogeneity of variable inputs in a translog production function. Additionally, Hou et al. (2024) adapted this approach for a stochastic frontier model, introducing a new efficiency estimator based on firm’s profit maximization behavior.

This research uses a proxy variable approach¹ to examine the consequences of agrochemical input reduction through a retrospective analysis of the growth factors of output and TFP. Specifically, it aims to evaluate the impact of fertilizers and pesticides—considered endogenous inputs—on the production and TFP growth of cereal producers. The empirical analysis focuses on the Czech Republic, where cereal production is a key component of agricultural output, accounting for 32% of total agricultural production (Czech Statistical Office, 2023). Compared to its neighbors, Austria and Germany, the Czech Republic relies on higher levels of fertilizer (nitrogen) and pesticide use to achieve comparable crop yields. This suggests a potential opportunity to reduce pollution while maintaining agricultural productivity (e.g. Wuepper et al., 2023; Wuepper et al., 2020). An in-depth analysis of the Czech farming system can identify constraints that hinder farmers from adopting production practices similar to those in Austria and Germany—where equivalent agricultural productivity is achieved with substantially lower environmental impact—and explore the necessary adjustments and support mechanisms to facilitate sustainable agricultural transitions.

The novelty of this study lies in its methodological approach, which evaluates how changes in chemical inputs affect output and TFP growth while addressing the endogeneity of these inputs. Our methodology builds on the existing proxy variable approach by incorporating a flexible representation of the production process, ensuring unbiased estimates of production function parameters and productivity. Additionally, it extends previous approaches by including multiple input variables, offering a more comprehensive analysis. At the empirical level, this study provides new and detailed insights into the role of pesticides and fertilizers in driving output and TFP growth, contributing critical information for agricultural policy formulation.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the theoretical background for decomposing output and TFP growth, based on the translog production function that addresses endogeneity. Section 3 outlines the identification and estimation procedures, while Section 4 describes the data used. Section 5 presents the results, followed by Section 6, which discusses the findings and their policy implications. Finally, Section 7 offers concluding remarks.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Production function and components of output growth

We start with the production function, which includes a neutral productivity component, and write it as

$$Y_{it} = F(X_{it}, Q_{it}, t) \exp(\omega_{it} + v_{it}), \quad (2.1)$$

where Y is output, X is the vector of variable inputs, Q is the vector of quasi-fixed (predetermined) inputs, and t is the time trend variable. ω is a persistent productivity shock (which is known and predictable to the farm) or Hicks-neutral productivity, while v represents a transitory productivity shock (which is unknown to farms or analysts). The subscript i denotes individual farms, while t represents time. Since ω_{it} is known to the farm, it can be viewed as an unobservable input (from the perspective of the analyst) that is separable from other inputs. Alternatively, it can also be viewed as a shifter of the production

¹ In general, when an input is endogenous, instrumental variables (IV) are required. However, in this case, we do not rely on external IVs. Instead, we address the issue of endogeneity by incorporating the first-order conditions (FOCs) with respect to each variable input. This method, known as the proxy variable approach, expresses the unobserved productivity term ω in terms of observable variables derived from the FOCs. In particular, this method does not require additional assumptions beyond profit maximization. The assumptions of the proxy variable approach with respect to our model specification are discussed in Section 3.1.2.

function. Incorporating a time-constant farm effect, we can rewrite the production as $Y_{it} = A(m_{it})F(X_{it}, Q_{it}, t) \exp(v_{it})$ where $\ln A(m_{it}) = \mu_i + \omega_{it}$, with μ_i representing farm-specific effects.²

To analyze the contribution of various factors to output growth, we take the total differential of Eq. (2.1) after applying a logarithmic transformation. After a few algebraic steps, this yields:

$$\dot{Y}_{it} = \sum_j E_{X_{jit}} \dot{X}_{jit} + \sum_m E_{Q_{mit}} \dot{Q}_{mit} + TC_{it} + \dot{\omega}_{it} + \dot{v}_{it}, \quad (2.2)$$

where $E_{X_{jit}}$ and $E_{Q_{mit}}$ represent the output elasticities of variable and quasi-fixed inputs, respectively. Technological change (TC) is defined as $TC = \partial \ln F(\cdot) / \partial t$, and a dot over a variable indicates its rate of change. The above formulation decomposes output growth into contributions from input use (both variable and quasi-fixed), TC, and productivity improvements ($\dot{\omega}$). For example, \dot{Y} can be increased by expanding input use, adopting improved technology, or improving productivity.

Rearranging Eq. (2.2) gives

$$T\dot{F}P_{it} = TC_{it} + (SRTS_{it} - 1) \sum_j S_{jit} \dot{X}_{jit} + \sum_m E_{Q_{mit}} \dot{Q}_{mit} + \dot{\omega}_{it}, \quad (2.3)$$

where $T\dot{F}P_{it} = \dot{Y}_{it} - \sum_j S_j \dot{X}_{jit}$, S_{jit} is the cost share, defined as $S_{jit} = W_{jit} X_{jit} / C_{it}$, where W_j is the price of the variable input X_j and C_{it} is total cost given by $C_{it} = \sum_j W_{jit} X_{jit}$. Short-run returns to scale (SRTS) are represented as $SRTS_{it} = \sum_j E_{X_{jit}}$. If input levels remain unchanged, the change in TFP has two components: TC and productivity growth $\dot{\omega}_{it}$. In this case, $T\dot{F}P$ is equivalent to \dot{Y} . These components can be identified, as will be discussed later.

However, TFP change is not always intuitive. In a microeconomic context, a positive TFP change for a farm does not necessarily indicate that it is making a profit. To better understand this relationship, we can relate the TFP change to the profitability change (Kumbhakar and Lien, 2009). Another intuitive decomposition involves breaking down output change into its key components such as TC, changes in input use (both quasi-fixed and variable), and productivity change. This approach helps to determine whether output growth is input-driven or TC-driven and quantifies their relative contributions. The decomposition is illustrated in Eq. (2.2).

To define profit change as a percentage of total cost, we start with the profit equation ($\pi = \sum_j PY - W_j X_j$) treating all inputs as variable for simplicity.

$$\frac{1}{C} \frac{d\pi}{dt} = \frac{PY}{C} \{ \dot{P} + \dot{Y} \} - \left\{ \sum_j S_j \dot{W}_j + \sum_j S_j \dot{X}_j \right\}. \quad (2.4)$$

2.2. Proxy variable approach

Our goal is to estimate a production function, but this process presents econometric challenges, as first identified by Marschak and Andrews (1944). They recognized that in real-world production, the relationship between inputs and output is often simultaneous, meaning that output influences input choices (e.g., firms adjust labor and capital based on output levels), while inputs also determine output. This simultaneous determination complicates the estimation of production functions, as the standard assumption of a one-directional causal relationship (where input determines output) does not hold. To correctly identify the production function, Marschak and Andrews (1944) argued that simultaneity must be explicitly accounted for. Their central contribution was to address the identification problem in production functions by incorporating simultaneity and random variables into the estimation process.

Marschak and Andrews (1944) emphasized that a valid production function must account for the fact that inputs are chosen based on economic behavior (e.g., profit maximization) and that unobservable

shocks affect both inputs and output. To address these challenges, they introduced the framework of simultaneous equations, which helps to identify the true relationship between inputs and output in production models. Their work laid the foundation for later econometric methods, such as estimators developed by Olley and Pakes (1996) and Levinsohn and Petrin (2003), which explicitly account for endogeneity and simultaneity in the estimation of the production function. Another common approach in the applied production literature is the use of instrumental variable (IV) estimators to address these issues. However, identifying valid external instrumental variables is often an ad hoc exercise. For this reason, we adopt the proxy variable approach, assuming expected profit maximization to address endogeneity and simultaneity. Specifically, we classify inputs into endogenous and exogenous (predetermined) categories to ensure a more robust estimation of the production function.

We employ a multi-step approach. In step 1, we use share equations (as proposed by Gandhi et al. (2020)), which exclude the persistent productivity shock ω and therefore are not subject to endogeneity (i.e., correlation between ω and variable inputs). In this step, we estimate the parameters associated with the variable inputs in the translog production function. We follow the literature that treats state variables as predetermined (Olley and Pakes, 1996; Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003; Gandhi et al., 2020), along with many others who have built on the framework introduced by Olley and Pakes in their well-known Econometrica paper. Economic reasoning is used to determine whether a variable is quasi-fixed or variable.

In Step 2, we treat the previously estimated (identified) parameters as known and incorporate them into the production function. In this step, a proxy for ω is used to estimate the remaining parameters. Once all parameters are estimated, we recover ω_{it} using the first-order conditions (FOCs).

The proxy variable approach works, in general, because (i) the FOCs are rewritten (inverted) to express the unobserved ω —which is correlated with the variable inputs, in terms of observables (inputs); and (ii) a Markov assumption is imposed on ω , allowing it to be expressed in terms of lagged values of the input variables and prices (variable inputs and output).

2.3. The production function specification

In this section, we parameterize the production function described in Eq. (2.1). We assume that the production process can be well approximated using a translog (TL) production function. Although the proxy variable approach often uses the Cobb–Douglas (CD) function, this functional form can be overly restrictive and may lead to biased results. The advantage of the TL function lies in its flexibility, as its second derivatives are non-zero and the CD function is nested within the TL function, allowing us to test the flexible form against the restrictive form.

Drawing on theoretical foundations and empirical evidence on adjustment costs (Hamermesh and Pfann, 1996; Cooper and Haltiwanger, 2006; Mishra et al., 2004; Yang and Shumway, 2016; Hu et al., 2020), our translog model treats capital (K), land (A) and labor (L) as quasi-fixed inputs (state variables). These factors face adjustment constraints, including time-to-install costs for capital equipment, binding lease agreements for land, as well as employment contracts and training requirements for labor. In contrast, material inputs—fertilizer (F), pesticides (H) (including herbicides and other crop protection products), and other material inputs (O)—are treated as freely varying factors without dynamic implications, allowing for instantaneous adjustment. Adjustment costs formalize the process of a farm's dynamic production decisions. Seeing as quasi-fixed inputs are subject to adjustment costs, farms determine their levels dynamically at time $t - 1$, making them predetermined state variables at time t . Variable inputs, by contrast, are chosen at time t , within the production period to maximize profit (short run). Additionally, we include a time variable as a proxy for

² It can capture time-invariant productivity as well because μ_i cannot be separated from ω_{it} if one writes the productivity component as $\omega_{it}^0 + \omega_{it}$.

technological change³ and account for farm-specific effects (μ_i). Finally, we express the production function (2.1) in logarithmic form as follows, where lowercase letters represent the logarithms of their uppercase counterparts:

$$y_{it} = f(k_{it}, a_{it}, l_{it}, f_{it}, h_{it}, o_{it}, t) + \mu_i + \omega_{it} + v_{it} \equiv f(q_{jit}, s_{rit}) + \mu_i + \omega_{it} + v_{it}, \quad (2.5)$$

where the variables in q_{jit} are $k_{it}, a_{it}, l_{it}, t$, and the variables in s_{rit} are f_{it}, h_{it}, o_{it} . The subscripts i and t denote the farm and time periods, respectively ($i = 1, \dots, n, t = 1, \dots, T$). The full translog form of $f(\cdot)$ can be expressed as

$$y_{it} = \mu_i + \sum_j \beta_j q_{jit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} q_{jit} q_{lit} + \sum_r \alpha_r s_{rit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_r \sum_{r'} \alpha_{rr'} s_{rit} s_{r'it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_r \delta_{jr} q_{jit} s_{rit} + \omega_{it} + v_{it} \quad (2.6)$$

with the symmetry restrictions on $\beta_{jl}, \alpha_{rr'}$ and δ_{jr} .

The above TL function $f(q_{jit}, s_{rit})$, where $j = k, a, l, t$ and $r = f, h, o$, can be written as $T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) + TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2)$, where

$$T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) = \sum_r \alpha_r s_{rit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_r \sum_{r'} \alpha_{rr'} s_{rit} s_{r'it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_r \delta_{jr} q_{jit} s_{rit}, \quad (2.7)$$

is a translog function with the variable inputs F, H, O and

$$TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) = \mu_i + \sum_j \beta_j q_{jit} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} q_{jit} q_{lit} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}, \quad (2.8)$$

is a translog function with the quasi-fixed inputs K, A, L and t .

We denote $\beta_1 = (\alpha_r, \alpha_{rr'}, \delta_{jr})$ and $\beta_2 = (\mu_i, \beta_j, \beta_{jl})$ for $r, r' = f, h, o$, and $j, l = k, a, l, t$. The full TL function with F, H, O and K, A, L, t is decomposed into two parts: the first part is a sub-translog function with F, H, O , while the remaining terms are included in the $TL(\cdot)$ function.

3. Identification and estimation

3.1. Identification

This section provides insights into the two-step identification of production function parameters and evaluates the assumptions underlying the proxy variable approach with respect to model specification and estimation strategy.

3.1.1. Two-step identifying procedure of production function parameters

The TL function in Eq. (2.6) is identified using a multi-step procedure. We assume that producers maximize their expected short-term profit and choose the variable inputs F, H, O in the current period, t , while the quasi-fixed inputs $Q \in (K, A, L)$ are predetermined (chosen at time $t - 1$). The persistent productivity shock ω is known to the farmer when making the optimal input decision.

Identification consists of several steps: the first step identifies the β_1 parameters, while the second step identifies the remaining parameters in β_2 . To achieve this, we first express ω_{it} in terms of observed data and the estimated parameters from Step 1 (β_1) using the FOCs. We then assume a Markov process for ω . These two features allow us to rewrite the production function in terms of β_2 and the dynamics of ω . The details of both steps are provided in Appendix A.

3.1.2. Proxy variable identifying assumptions

In the industrial organization (IO) literature, the identification of production functions using the proxy variable approach typically rests on several assumptions (Olley and Pakes, 1996; Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003): (i) monotonicity of the proxy variables, implying a consistent relationship with productivity and no heterogeneous effects; (ii) exogeneity of the state variables with respect to contemporaneous shocks; (iii) timing of input choices, such that variable inputs depend on both

³ Since technological change has a long term character, t is included among quasi-fixed inputs.

observed and unobserved current productivity, while state variables depend only on past productivity; (iv) functional-form restrictions on the production function; (v) validity of the proxies, in that they respond to productivity shocks observed by the firm and are not driven by unobserved factors; (vi) absence of selection bias due to the exit of less productive firms; and (vii) absence of measurement error in input variables. We evaluated these assumptions in relation to our model specification and econometric framework.

The first assumption is a necessary condition for identifying parameters when using a non-parametric production function. However, if a parametric production function is employed, monotonicity is not required for at least two reasons: (i) identification does not depend on inverting a production function to obtain unobservable variables, and (ii) estimation relies on functional-form and orthogonality assumptions rather than on monotonicity.⁴⁵ Thus, the monotonicity of the proxy variables is not required to test in the parametric approach adopted in our study.

Second, our model follows the IO literature in which some inputs are considered quasi-fixed (state variables)—determined in the previous period (known as the timing assumption). From an econometric perspective, these variables are treated as predetermined at time t . A dynamic optimization model based on the sequential decision process in crop production can be used to determine the state variables. In particular, the decision process can be divided into (i) the planting season and (ii) the growing and harvest season. The decision regarding the planted area is based on the information during the planting season in time $t - 1$, while yield is determined using information from the growing season in the period of time t .⁶

Regarding the third assumption, variable inputs are chosen by maximizing the short-term (variable) profit, where the persistent productivity shock, ω , is observed by the farm (the decision-maker) but not by researchers. This is an important assumption, as the random productivity shock, v , is always assumed to be unobservable in agricultural production. Thus, while the farm observes the persistent productivity shock, ω , it does not observe the random productivity shock, v . Consequently, expected profit maximization is applied, which removes the unobserved v from the expected profit expression. In this short-term framework, the current value of ω is used. Lagged values appear in the estimating equation due to the Markov assumption on ω , but the model itself does not incorporate past productivity directly. We assess this assumption using the second specification test described below.

With respect to functional-form assumptions, the CD specification remains the most widely used in the literature. However, it has several well-documented limitations.⁷ In this study, we employ a flexible func-

⁴ Specifically, the persistent productivity shock ω can be analytically expressed in terms of observable variables. The general idea is that endogenous variables (demand functions) can be solved in terms of prices and quasi-fixed inputs. For instance, assuming CD production function, $S = S(K, A, L, P, W_S, \omega)$, it can be inverted to express $\omega = S^{-1}(K, A, L, S, P, W_S)$ where K, A, L are quasi-fixed inputs, S is the variable input, P is the output price, and W_S is the price of the variable input S . The function $S(\cdot)$ is invertible when it is monotonic, as demonstrated by Levinsohn and Petrin (2003). For a CD function, $\ln Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_K \ln K_{it} + \beta_A \ln A_{it} + \beta_L \ln L_{it} + \beta_S \ln S_{it} + \omega_{it} + v_{it}$, the FOC with respect to S is $W_{S_{it}} S_{it} / P_{it} Y_{it} = \beta_S \theta \exp(-v_{it})$, where $\theta = \mathbb{E}[\exp(v_{it})]$. This implies that $\omega_{it} = -\ln(\beta_S \theta) + \ln(W_S / P)_{it} + (1 - \beta_S) \ln S_{it} - \beta_K \ln K_{it} - \beta_A \ln A_{it} - \beta_L \ln L_{it}$. Here, the demand function for S is always invertible.

⁵ Moreover, farm-level heterogeneity (if relevant) can be incorporated into the production function through farm fixed effects.

⁶ Our distinction is therefore grounded in the intrinsic characteristics of the agricultural production process rather than solely econometric considerations. The sequential decision process is also supported by the composition of our sample: crop production accounts for 74.3% of total agricultural output, indicating its dominance within the production structure. Moreover, we indirectly validate this assumption through our first specification test (Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003).

⁷ Restrictions of CD function include unitary elasticity of substitution, constant production elasticities, and perfect substitutability of inputs, etc.

tional form—the translog production function—and test this against the more restrictive CD specification. This generalization, employed in our study, helps address limitations associated with restrictive functional-form assumptions.

The proxy validity assumption, tested by the first and the second specification tests, is crucial for empirical applications. In our study, the proxy for the scalar unobservable ω_{it} is derived from the FOCs of expected profit maximization. Together with the Markov process assumption on ω_{it} , this expresses ω_{it} in terms of lagged observed variables. The unobserved variable in the proxy is η_{it} , where $\omega_{it} = \rho\omega_{it-1} + \eta_{it}$. The term η_{it} is assumed to be independent of all variables at times t and $t - 1$, and remains unobserved. This assumption is verified using the second specification test.

The sixth assumption is introduced for convenience. Empirical evidence shows that it has no impact on results (see footnote 21 of Levinsohn and Petrin (2003)). Therefore, this assumption is routinely adopted in all applications. The final assumption (no measurement error) is standard in all econometric models.⁸

To summarize, we employ a Wald test to test the functional form and two specification tests to verify the identifying assumptions (Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003). Specifically, the first specification test checks whether consistent estimates are obtained when inputs are split differently into quasi-fixed and variable categories. The second specification test examines whether inputs at times t and $t - 1$ are correlated with innovations in productivity at time t .⁹ Following Levinsohn and Petrin (2003) and Olley and Pakes (1996), we therefore test the proxy validity assumption by examining the correlation between input choices and contemporaneous productivity innovations. An insignificant correlation supports the assumption that the proxies reflect observed productivity shocks rather than unobserved factors.

3.2. Estimation

This section briefly discusses the parameter estimation process, which is performed in three steps using nonlinear least squares (NLS) and the nonlinear mixed-effect model estimator (NLME).

3.2.1. Step 1

In this step, we use the FOCs with respect to material inputs to estimate the parameters in $T(\cdot)$, i.e., β_1 . The relevant equations are given in (A.4), $\ln s_{Sit} = \ln(\varepsilon_{Sit}\theta) - v_{it}$, $S \in F, H, O$. Given that v is i.i.d. and uncorrelated with the variables in ε_S , we use NLS to estimate β_1 following Bates and Watts (1988), Bates and Chambers (1992), and Moré (1978). Note that ω does not appear in the share equations, so no assumptions about it are required to estimate them. The only assumption is that the error term v is uncorrelated with the inputs—both quasi-fixed and variable. The procedure is as follows:

We perform NLS regressions of $\ln s_{Fit}$ on $\ln(\varepsilon_{Fit}\theta)$ and obtain the fitted values $\ln(\widehat{\varepsilon_{Fit}\theta})$ and $-\widehat{v}_{it}$. Using \widehat{v}_{it} , we estimate θ from $\widehat{\theta} = \mathbb{E}[\exp(\widehat{v}_{it})]$. We then perform additional NLS regressions $\ln s_{Hit}$ on $\ln(\varepsilon_{Hit}\theta)$ and $\ln s_{Oit}$ on $\ln(\varepsilon_{Oit}\theta)$, respectively, to obtain the fitted values: (i) $\ln(\widehat{\varepsilon_{Hit}\theta})$ and $-\widehat{v}_{it}$, and (ii) $\ln(\widehat{\varepsilon_{Oit}\theta})$ and $-\widehat{v}_{it}$. Then, we use \widehat{v}_{it} from these NLS regressions to obtain the second and third estimates of θ using $\widehat{\theta} = \mathbb{E}[\exp(\widehat{v}_{it})]$. Finally, we compute an average of these three

⁸ To the best of our knowledge, no studies explicitly address measurement error in the covariates. In particular, the IO literature does not provide guidance on handling measurement errors in inputs, especially within structural approaches (proxy variable methods) commonly applied in the estimation of production functions. This remains an important area for future research.

⁹ Levinsohn and Petrin (2003) test for the correlation between inputs in period t and innovations in productivity in period $t + 1$. However, in an unbalanced panel datasets, it is methodologically more appropriate and statistically more reliable to examine the correlation between lagged inputs and current innovations in productivity. This approach is also consistent with standard practice in dynamic panel models (Baltagi, 2021; Wooldridge, 2002).

estimates of θ . The estimated parameters in these NLS regressions represent $\beta_1 \times \theta$. Finally, we use the estimated value of θ to obtain estimates of β_1 by dividing each of the NLS parameters by $\widehat{\theta}$.

3.2.2. Step 2

In this step, we estimate the parameters in β_2 . The estimating equation is (A.12):

$$\bar{y}_{it} = TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} - \rho TL(q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) + e_{it} \tag{3.1}$$

where $e_{it} = v_{it} + \eta_{it}$ with η_{it} is an i.i.d. productivity innovation uncorrelated with S_{it} , where $S \in F, H, O$, and any other variables in the model. $\bar{R}_{it-1} = [RF_{it-1} + RH_{it-1} + RO_{it-1}]/3$ and RF_{it-1} , RH_{it-1} , RO_{it-1} are known/estimated, since they consist of data and estimated parameters from Step 1.

Remark 1. Since $TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2)$ includes μ_i , which is likely to be correlated with $f_{it}, f_{it-1}, h_{it}, h_{it-1}, o_{it}, o_{it-1}$ and possibly other variables in the $TL(\cdot)$ function, we must first address this issue before estimating (3.1).

Rewriting $TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) - \rho TL(q_{jit-1}; \beta_2)$ fully to bring μ_i to light using (2.8) and taking a lag, yields $TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) - \rho TL(q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) = \mu_i(1 - \rho) + \sum_j \beta_j(q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}]$. We then substitute this in (3.1) to obtain:

$$\bar{y}_{it} = \mu_i(1 - \rho) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} + \sum_j \beta_j(q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}] + e_{it}. \tag{3.2}$$

Applying first differencing (FD) to Eq. (3.2) eliminates μ_i allowing us to estimate the equation using NLS.¹⁰ Note that ρ is identified from the coefficient of \bar{R}_{it-1} and the β_2 coefficients are identified from the first differences of $\sum_j \beta_j(q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}]$.

However, FD has a drawback: the presence of lagged variables results in a loss of two observations for each i (a total of $2N$ observations) due to the presence of two lags. An alternative to FD is the correlated random effects model, where $\mu_i = z_i' \gamma_i + \xi_i$ where z_i are time-invariant variables correlated with those in (3.2), i.e., q_{jit} and $q_{jit-1} \forall j$. In the absence of any z_i variables, one can use Mundlak's (1978) formulation which replaces z_i with the mean farm-level values of q_j , i.e., \bar{q}_j , $j = k, a, l, t$. That is,

$$\mu_i = \sum_j \gamma_j \bar{q}_j + \chi_i, \quad j = k, a, l, t \tag{3.3}$$

where χ_i is not correlated with the right-hand-side variables in (3.2). Having identified β_1 and β_2 , we can estimate ω_{it} by averaging ω_{it} from Eqs. (A.5), (A.6) and (A.7).

Since FD of (3.4) will involve two lags, we use the correlated random effects formulation of Mundlak (1978) to save one observation for each i , i.e. in total N observations. That is, we use (3.3) in (3.4) and estimate γ_j together with the other parameters in (3.4). The final model to be estimated empirically is the following:

$$\bar{y}_{it} = (\sum_j \gamma_j \bar{q}_j + \chi_i)(1 - \rho) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} + \sum_j \beta_j(q_{jit} - \rho q_{jit-1}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_l \beta_{jl} [q_{jit} q_{lit} - \rho q_{jit-1} q_{lit-1}] + e_{it} \tag{3.4}$$

Given the presence of the χ_i term, we use NLME¹¹ to estimate (3.4).

¹⁰ Moreover, the standard errors can be corrected for possible heteroscedasticity. In particular, we can incorporate some exogenous variables z_{it} into Eq. (A.8) to account for factors influencing productivity. This allows identification of key drivers of productivity growth.

¹¹ NLME is a generalization of linear mixed-effects model, where the conditional mean of the outcome, given the random effects, is a non-linear function of both the coefficients and random effects (StataCorp, 2023).

3.2.3. Step 3

Productivity (ω_{it}) is estimated by averaging ω_{it} from Eqs. (A.5), (A.6) and (A.7). After estimating ω_{it} , we can estimate the productivity change component ($\dot{\omega}_{it}$) as:

$$\dot{\omega}_{it} = \omega_{it} - \omega_{it-1} \quad (3.5)$$

Given the significant variation in farm sizes, we employ an aggregate weighted productivity metric and its decomposition to analyze the impact of farm size on overall productivity. In particular, the weighted aggregate productivity (Olley and Pakes, 1996) is given by:

$$\omega_t = \sum_i W_{it} \omega_{it} \quad (3.6)$$

where: $W_{it} = Y_{it} / \sum_i Y_{it}$. The weighted aggregate productivity can be decomposed to unweighted average productivity and the covariance between output and productivity level (Kumbhakar and Li, 2024):

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_t &= \sum_i W_{it} \omega_{it} = \sum_i [\bar{W}_t + (W_{it} - \bar{W}_t)] [\bar{\omega}_t + (\omega_{it} - \bar{\omega}_t)] \\ &= \bar{\omega}_t + \sum_i (W_{it} - \bar{W}_t) (\omega_{it} - \bar{\omega}_t) \equiv \bar{\omega}_t + cov_t \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

where $\bar{\omega}_t = 1/N_t \sum_i \omega_{it}$ is the unweighted average productivity, $\bar{W}_t = 1/N_t$ represents the unweighted output share and $cov_t \equiv \sum_i (W_{it} - \bar{W}_t) (\omega_{it} - \bar{\omega}_t)$ is sample covariance between output share and productivity. Here, ω_t is the mean of persistent productivity over farms at time t , while cov_t measures the extent to which additional resources are allocated to more productive farms. The change in mean productivity $\Delta\omega_t$ and the change in covariance Δcov_t represent the strength of the association between output share and productivity change. That is, the larger the covariance, the greater the contribution of farms with high-output farms to the weighted aggregate productivity change: $\Delta\omega_t = \Delta\bar{\omega}_t + \Delta cov_t$.

4. Data

This study uses farm-level data derived from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), a comprehensive database containing harmonized microeconomic data for agricultural holdings. Our initial sample consists of 10,799 observations from the two most prominent farming types contributing to cereal production in the Czech Republic: field crop farms and mixed farms, covering the period 2008 to 2020. Specifically, field crop farms account for 55% observations, while mixed crop and livestock farms 45%.

The model differentiates between three variable inputs: fertilizers, pesticides, and other materials; three quasi-fixed inputs: land, capital, and labor; and one output variable representing aggregate production. Fertilizers (F) refer to the cost of purchasing fertilizers and soil improvers. Pesticides (H) are the cost of purchasing plant protection products, traps and baits, bird scarers, anti-hail shells, frost protection, etc. (excluding those used for forests). Other materials (O) are calculated as the sum of the total specific costs and total agricultural overhead, excluding fertilizers and pesticides. The land (A) is measured in hectares of the Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA). Capital (K) is measured as the total current assets. Labor (L) is measured in the Annual Work Unit (AWU). The output variable (Y) represents the aggregate production and is calculated as the sum of the value of cereal production, other crop production (measured as the difference between the total value of crop production and the value of cereal production) and other farm output (which is the sum of cow's milk and milk products, other livestock production and other farm-generated production). Table B.1 in Appendix B provides the FADN codes for these variables.

The monetary variables are deflated using the price indices for the Czech Republic from the EUROSTAT database (2010 = 100). Capital input is adjusted for inflation using the index of purchase prices for agricultural production inputs, specifically for materials. The price index for fertilizers and soil adjusts the fertilizer input. The price index for

plant protection products and pesticides is used to adjust the pesticide input. The price index of goods and services currently consumed in agriculture is used to deflate the other input materials. The output variable is deflated using the producer price indices of agricultural products (output), namely, the price index for the cereals, the price index for the crops, the price index of milk and milk products, the price index for animal production and the price index for the production of agricultural inputs. In addition, this study incorporates the price index for the production of agricultural goods (excluding fruits and vegetables, P).

Since not all agricultural holdings in the database contain complete information, observations with zero values of cereal production, land, labor, capital, and material are excluded from the dataset. Furthermore, holdings with less than three consecutive years of observations are excluded from the sample. This procedure allows for the use of lags and Mundlak's device, while also reducing issues related to the entry and exit of agricultural holdings in the database. After this data cleaning procedure, the final dataset consists of 7,269 observations. Table 1 presents the summary statistics for the input and output variables.

Furthermore, all log-transformed variables are normalized by dividing them by their respective sample means. This allows the first-order parameters to be interpreted as output elasticities of the respective inputs evaluated at the sample mean. We adopt this approach because it simplifies the interpretation of the estimates.

5. Results

5.1. Production function parameter estimates

The estimated parameters are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The tables indicate that the parameters conventionally analyzed in the production function estimates are highly significant. This applies to all first-order coefficients as well as the majority of second-order parameters and productivity term. The statistical significance of the second-order parameters supports the use of a flexible translog form over the more restrictive CD production function. This is formally confirmed by the Wald test, which rejects the null hypothesis of imposing zero restrictions on the second-order parameters, even at 1% significance level ($\chi^2 : 1156.5$, p -value = 0.000). In other words, the application of the CD function, as seen in numerous proxy variable literature studies, could lead to biased results. In addition, the estimation results are evaluated based on whether the estimated parameters satisfy the theoretical consistency conditions of production technology. Theoretically, a production function should be nondecreasing in inputs (monotonicity) and concave in inputs (diminishing marginal returns). The monotonicity conditions for the inputs require $\alpha_r > 0$ for $r = f, h, o$; and $\beta_j > 0$ for $j = k, a, l$, respectively. The concavity condition (diminishing marginal returns) requires: $\alpha_{rr} + \alpha_r^2 - \alpha_r < 0$ for $r = f, h, o$; and $\beta_{rr} + \beta_r^2 - \beta_r < 0$ for $r = k, a, l$, respectively. Tables 2 and 3 show that these conditions are met by the estimates.¹²

The first specification test suggests the robustness of the model across alternative specifications and validates the correct choice of proxy variables. In particular, Table B.2 in Appendix B presents alternative model estimates: Model 1—baseline model with 3 variable and 3 quasi-fixed inputs; Model 2—with 2 variable inputs (fertilizers and pesticides aggregated into a single agrochemical input) and 3 quasi-fixed inputs; Model 3—with 4 variable and 2 quasi-fixed inputs; and Model 4—with 3 variable and 2 quasi-fixed inputs. The results indicate consistent robustness across these models. Moreover, Table B.3 shows

¹² We restrict our attention to the first principle minors of the Hessian (the matrix of second derivatives of the production function) because our analysis requires only diminishing returns to scale, not convex technologies. While convexity implies diminishing returns to scale, the reverse is not necessarily true.

Table 1
Summary statistics of input and output variables.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Land [hectares]	7269	908.7	983.4	6.5	10160.3
Capital [1,000 CZK]	7269	24200.0	34000.0	30.0	391000.0
Labor [AWU]	7269	23.6	29.6	0.2	232.5
Fertilizers [1,000 CZK]	7269	2581.8	3383.6	1.6	52300.0
Pesticides [1,000 CZK]	7269	2446.3	3075.3	1.3	29100.0
Other materials [1,000 CZK]	7269	20000.0	26800.0	95.1	211000.0
Output [1,000 CZK]	7269	29600.0	38800.0	93.7	310000.0

Table 2
Estimates of input elasticity coefficients (step 1).

Variable input - Fertilizers				
Variable	Coef.	Std.Err.	p-value	Recalculated coef.
const.	0.086	0.000	0.000	0.081
<i>f</i>	0.017	0.000	0.000	0.016
<i>h</i>	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005
<i>o</i>	-0.032	0.001	0.000	-0.030
<i>a</i>	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.021
<i>l</i>	-0.010	0.001	0.000	-0.009
<i>k</i>	-0.002	0.001	0.001	-0.002
<i>t</i>	-0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.001
Variable input - Pesticides				
Variable	Coef.	Std.Err.	p-value	Recalculated coef.
const.	0.076	0.000	0.000	0.072
<i>h</i>	0.016	0.000	0.000	0.015
<i>f</i>	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005
<i>o</i>	-0.017	0.001	0.000	-0.016
<i>a</i>	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.012
<i>l</i>	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.008
<i>k</i>	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.007
<i>t</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Variable input - Other materials				
Variable	Coef.	Std.Err.	p-value	Recalculated coef.
const.	0.646	0.002	0.000	0.608
<i>o</i>	0.236	0.005	0.000	0.222
<i>f</i>	-0.062	0.004	0.000	-0.059
<i>h</i>	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037
<i>a</i>	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002
<i>l</i>	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.082
<i>k</i>	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.050
<i>t</i>	-0.004	0.000	0.000	-0.004

Note: The estimated coefficients are $\beta_1 \times \theta$. Estimates of β_1 (Recalculated coef.) are obtained by dividing each of the NLS parameters by estimated $\hat{\theta}$ (see Section 3.2.1 for details).

no significant differences in the first-order parameters (production elasticities). Figs. B.1 further illustrate that the dynamics of productivity change remain consistent across specifications, while Table B.4 provides statistical evidence of no significant differences in productivity change under alternative model structures.

The second specification test evaluates the assumptions of proxy validity. Specifically, it tests whether production inputs in t and $t - 1$ are uncorrelated with productivity innovations in time t . Table B.5 in Appendix B confirms that this condition holds across all estimates, even at the 1% significance level.

Table 2 presents the estimated parameters for the variable inputs. Specifically, the coefficients represent the first derivatives of the production function with respect to each variable input. The constant term corresponds to the first-order parameter of the production function, i.e., the output elasticity of respective input evaluated at the sample mean. The parameters for variable and quasi-fixed inputs correspond to the squared and cross-product terms, respectively. Finally, the parameter for the time variable provides information on biased technological change.¹³

¹³ The time variable is commonly used in applied production analysis as a proxy for technological change. However, it may also capture additional

The estimated elasticities of the variable inputs indicate that the overall impact of material inputs is 0.761.¹⁴ This value aligns with other studies on Czech agriculture (e.g., Bokusheva and Čechura, 2017) and reflects the material input shares in our dataset. The elasticities of fertilizers and pesticides are similar, at 0.081 and 0.072, respectively. In other words, fertilizers and pesticides account for one-fifth of the impact of material input, suggesting their considerable role in overall production. Furthermore, the role of fertilizers and pesticides increases in material-intensive production systems, as indicated by the second-order parameters. These inputs also complement each other, unlike other material inputs. Increased fertilizer use can indirectly create favorable conditions for pests, diseases, and weeds, which, in turn, increases the demand for pesticides to protect crops (Ogada et al., 2021). Additionally, the use of fertilizers, pesticides, and other materials increases with land input, but decreases with labor and capital input. This indicates that larger farms tend to have higher material intensity, including greater fertilizer and pesticide use. This aligns with trends in the Czech Republic, where extensive farming systems with lower chemical inputs, particularly organic farming, are primarily small enterprises. In fact, 75% of organic farming enterprises operate on farms of up to 100 hectares (Hlaváčková et al., 2023).

Table 3 presents the estimated output elasticities of quasi-fixed inputs. The results reveal that land has the greatest impact on production, with an output elasticity of 0.162. The elasticities of labor and capital are almost the same magnitude, about 0.09 each. The elasticity of land declines in land-intensive production systems. In contrast, the elasticities of labor and capital increase in capital-intensive and labor-intensive production systems. The mutual cross-product parameters indicate a negative association between land and both labor and capital inputs as well as a positive association between labor and capital. These findings are consistent with the first-step results for variable inputs, offering important implications for agricultural production systems and their developmental trajectory. These findings suggest that expanding land use in land-intensive systems may be less effective for increasing output than optimizing other inputs or enhancing land productivity through technological and sustainable practices. Investments in workforce skills, technological advancements, and capital improvements yield proportionally higher returns than land expansion, reinforcing the need for modernization and efficiency-driven strategies in Czech agriculture.

The sum of the first-order parameters is 1.114, suggesting only limited economies of scale at the mean of the data. This indicates that farms, on average, operate close to their optimal scale, meaning the benefits of expanding farm size are relatively modest. However, second-order parameters of variable and quasi-fixed inputs suggest that economies of scale are less pronounced in land-intensive farms, whereas they are more significant in material-, labor-, and capital-intensive farms. Estimated scale returns also provide insight into the shadow shares of inputs.¹⁵ These shadow shares are: fertilizers (0.073),

factors, such as climate change or land degradation, if they follow a similar deterministic trend.

¹⁴ The overall impact of material inputs represents the sum of the elasticities fertilizers, pesticides and other material inputs.

¹⁵ The input shadow shares are calculated as estimated output elasticities divided by returns to scale. That is, the shadow share of the input represents the elasticities of the output in production with constant returns to scale.

Table 3
Production function estimates (step 2).

Variable	Coef.	Std.Error	p-value	Variable	Coef.	Std.Error	p-value
R	0.029	0.014	0.034	$a \times k$	-0.037	0.010	0.000
a	0.162	0.022	0.000	$l \times k$	0.039	0.013	0.002
l	0.093	0.016	0.000	$a \times t$	0.010	0.002	0.000
k	0.098	0.009	0.000	$l \times t$	0.001	0.002	0.499
t	0.001	0.001	0.214	$k \times t$	-0.002	0.001	0.049
a^2	-0.005	0.022	0.811	\hat{q}_a	-0.137	0.025	0.000
l^2	0.079	0.025	0.001	\hat{q}_l	0.018	0.021	0.390
k^2	0.067	0.009	0.000	\hat{q}_k	0.011	0.014	0.412
t^2	0.005	0.000	0.000	\hat{q}_t	0.007	0.002	0.004
$a \times l$	-0.021	0.020	0.300	const.	-0.074	0.029	0.010

Note: R represents $\bar{R}_{it-1} = [RF_{it-1} + RH_{it-1} + RO_{it-1}]/3$, see estimated model formulation in (3.4). $\hat{q}_j, j = k, a, l, t$ represent group means of particular variables (see Mundlak's (1978) formulation).

Fig. 1. Sources of output growth.

pesticides (0.065); other materials (0.546), with a total shadow share for material inputs of 0.683; land (0.145); labor (0.083); and capital (0.088).

Technological change has a positive impact on production, and this impact accelerates over time. However, the first-order parameter is not statistically significant, suggesting that technological change only becomes important later in the study period. Since the cross parameters of fertilizers, pesticides, and other material, as well as those of quasi-fixed inputs (except for labor), are statistically significant, Hicks-neutral technological change can be rejected in favor of biased technological change¹⁶ (formally confirmed by the F-test). Specifically, technological change exhibits the following patterns: it is material- and capital-saving, while being land-using. However, given the magnitude of the estimated parameters, the overall impact of biased technological change is limited.

5.2. Sources of output and TFP growth

Fig. 1 illustrates the dynamics of output growth and its underlying sources.¹⁷ Output growth follows a strong upward trend from 2010 to 2015, then declines in 2016 and 2017, returning to 2013 levels before recovering in the subsequent years. Productivity changes are identified as the main driver of output growth, with their dynamics closely mirroring those of overall output growth (see Table B.6 in Appendix B for reference).

Additionally, variable inputs and technological change also contribute significantly to output growth. Variable inputs have a positive

¹⁶ Biased technological change offers valuable insights into the dynamics of input shadow shares, reflecting shifts in input productivity driven by technological advancements, including the adoption of new technologies and innovations.

¹⁷ Sources of output growth are given by Eq. (2.2).

Fig. 2. Sources of TFP growth.

effect in the first half of the study period but contribute negatively in the latter part. Technological change exerts a positive impact on output growth toward the end of the period under investigation. Quasi-fixed inputs, however, do not contribute to output growth. The observed patterns indicate a transition from intensive agriculture to more sustainable practices, aligning with the evolution of agricultural policy frameworks and their implementation.

The dynamics of TFP closely follow those of output growth (see Fig. 2 and Table B.7 in Appendix B). The drivers¹⁸ of TFP growth are also similar, with productivity changes being their primary factor. Variable inputs are the second most significant contributor to TFP dynamics. However, unlike output growth, variable inputs have a considerable negative impact in the first half of the study period. In the second half, the positive and negative impacts of variable inputs closely mirror the fluctuations in TFP growth. Similar to output growth, technological change, similar to its role in output growth, has a positive impact toward the end of the study period. Quasi-fixed inputs do not significantly influence TFP growth.

The agricultural productivity of the farm is commonly characterized by considerable heterogeneity. Fig. 3 illustrates the distribution of productivity changes across the study period, highlighting that productivity dynamics vary widely among farms. The pronounced heterogeneity is a key characteristic of Czech cereal production. Moreover, given the substantial dual structure in Czech agriculture, where farm sizes differ significantly,¹⁹ we constructed an aggregate productivity measure using output weights (see Eq. (3.6)). The dynamics of weighted aggregate productivity change can be broken down into the unweighted average productivity change (as discussed earlier); and the sample covariance between output share and productivity level. Both are depicted in Appendix B Table B.8.²⁰

The dynamics of productivity appear to be shaped by multiple factors, including management quality, weather conditions, and farming practices. For example, between 2012 and 2015, productivity exhibited an upward trend, driven by favorable weather conditions, stable overwintering, and the optimal distribution of rainfall during the growing season. In contrast, extreme weather events negatively affected cereal

¹⁸ Sources of TFP growth are given by Eq. (2.3).

¹⁹ Duality in Czech agriculture is discussed by Cechura et al. (2022), Redlichová et al. (2023), Lososová et al. (2023).

²⁰ The table indicates that there are no considerable differences between weighted and unweighted productivity changes. This suggests that farm size, represented by output level, does not significantly affect the productivity dynamics. However, a slight decrease in covariance during the second half of the study period may imply that small farms have contributed increasingly to weighted aggregate productivity changes. Furthermore, this trend may also indicate that more resources are being allocated to more productive farms, specifically to smaller farms.

Fig. 3. Productivity change distribution.

production in 2017, as cereals experienced temperature stress and water deficits during critical growth stages²¹.

Agricultural policy underwent significant transformations during the study period, reflecting a shift toward greater environmental responsibility, sustainable rural development, and more targeted financial support mechanisms. Since 2015, greening measures and young farmers' payments have been incorporated into the direct payments scheme. These policy changes may have influenced productivity dynamics, as numerous studies have documented productivity shifts driven by policy instruments (Biagini et al., 2023; Nilsson, 2017; Khafagy and Vigani, 2022; Mary, 2013; Rizov et al., 2013). However, the existing literature does not provide a definitive conclusion regarding the impact of subsidies on productivity. The heterogeneous effects of subsidies are attributed to the varying objectives and implementation, which in turn influence farmers' behavior and productivity in diverse ways (Biagini et al., 2023; Nilsson, 2017).

5.3. Variable input dynamics and simulation of policy scenarios

The drivers of variable input dynamics are illustrated in Fig. 4 (for details, see Table B.9 in Appendix B). The figure indicates that the variable input dynamics are influenced by all variable inputs—namely fertilizers, pesticides, and other materials—in the first half of the study period, while in the second half, they are primarily driven by fertilizers and other materials. Fertilizers appear to have a mostly positive impact on variable input dynamics throughout the study period, with a stronger influence in the first half. Pesticides exhibit a considerable positive impact in the early years, followed by a small negative impact later on. Other materials show fluctuations that mirror the overall changes in variable inputs, with varying contributions over time. Most importantly, since variable inputs are key drivers of both output and TFP growth, Fig. 4 highlights the essential role of fertilizers and pesticides in shaping agricultural productivity.

The critical role of fertilizers and pesticides in driving output and TFP growth can have significant implications for the objectives of the Farm-to-Fork strategy. As discussed in the introduction, this strategy aims to: (i) reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%, resulting in a minimum 20% reduction in fertilizer use by 2030; and (ii) reduce the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% by 2030. The following sections will explore the potential ramifications of reducing agrochemicals within the context of Czech agriculture.

²¹ As demonstrated by Lesk et al. (2016), Beillouin et al. (2020), Devot et al. (2023), droughts and extreme heat significantly reduce cereal production, particularly when these climatic extremes occur during critical stages of the growing season.

Fig. 4. Decomposition of variable inputs dynamics.

Table 4 presents the results of simulations for different scenarios.²² The baseline scenario reflects conditions in 2020, the final year of the study. The simulations illustrate the impact of different levels of fertilizer and pesticide reductions²³ on overall agricultural output.

Table 4 shows that a 10% overall reduction in fertilizer and pesticide use (Scenario 1) compared to 2020 leads to a 3.5% decrease in agricultural output, with corresponding reductions in the shadow shares of fertilizers and pesticides by 4.2% and 4.9%, respectively. Scenario 2 models a 10% reduction in fertilizers and a 20% reduction in pesticides, leading to a 4.2% decrease in output and reductions in the shadow shares of fertilizers and pesticides by 4.6% and 6.6%, respectively. Finally, Scenario 3 assumes a 20% reduction in both fertilizers and pesticides, resulting in a 5.4% decrease in agricultural output and declines in fertilizer and pesticide shadow shares by 6.1% and 7.1%, respectively.

6. Discussion

In line with previous research (Beckman et al., 2020; Bremmer et al., 2021; Jost et al., 2025), the results indicate the considerable impact of fertilizer and pesticide reduction on agricultural output. This suggests that efforts to reduce reliance on agrochemicals could substantially affect farm productivity and profitability. However, estimated output reductions represent an upper bound of expected effects, as they do not account for farmer adaptation strategies. Farmers can mitigate reductions in agrochemical input by adopting alternative management practices, such as cover cropping, mechanical interventions, biological pest control, and various crop rotations (Weisberger et al., 2019; Riemens et al., 2022; Bremmer et al., 2021). Implementing adaptive practices requires adjustments in other material inputs, labor and capital (Beckman et al., 2020). This is consistent with the larger economic patterns observed in the estimation of the production function, which highlight the role of enhancing labor- and capital-intensive systems as a pathway for agricultural development that reduces the reliance on agrochemical inputs. However, considering the ongoing outflow of labor from agriculture, these adaptations will likely manifest predominantly through increased capital intensification rather than increased labor

²² The scenarios were selected to assess the sensitivity of production to fertilizer and pesticide reductions, providing insights into the potential impacts of the Farm-to-Fork strategy. While they do not exactly consider a 50% pesticide reduction, they reflect the strategy's framework. A direct simulation of such a large reduction would be biased, as it would not account for farmers' adaptation over time until 2030.

²³ The reduction does not represent the overall decrease of fertilizers and pesticides use of each farmer. Instead, a limit is imposed on the intensity of fertilizers and pesticides use per hectare. This limit represents the maximum intensity of use per hectare that cannot be exceeded by farmers, leading to an overall targeted reduction in fertilizers and pesticides use.

Table 4
Scenario simulations: Impact of reduced fertilizers and pesticides use compared to the baseline.

Simulation	Change				
	Fertilizers	Pesticides	Output	Fertilizer shadow share	Pesticides shadow share
Baseline = year 2020	1.00	1.00	1.000	1.000	1.000
Scenario 1	0.90	0.90	0.965	0.958	0.951
Scenario 2	0.90	0.80	0.958	0.954	0.934
Scenario 3	0.80	0.80	0.946	0.939	0.929

input (Jurkėnaitė et al., 2022). Nonetheless, the adoption of innovative agricultural technologies must be supported by a skilled workforce capable of effectively operating them (Marinouidi et al., 2019).

Consistent with the positive contribution of technological change to output and TFP growth in the later years of the study—when Czech farmers increasingly adopted precision farming technologies (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2023b)—the potential adverse effects of reducing agrochemical inputs could be addressed or mitigated through technological advancements. Czech agriculture could benefit from the widespread adoption of precision farming technologies, such as soil mapping, variable-rate applications, remote sensing, and smart fertilizer management systems for optimized fertilizer management (Agrahari et al., 2021; Heyl et al., 2023). Advanced pest and weed control methods, such as drone-based detection, site-specific spraying utilizing real-time sensors, and robotic mechanical weeding, offer promising solutions in pest and weed management (Anastasiou et al., 2023). Empirical evidence supports the positive impact of these technologies on agricultural productivity (Carrer et al., 2022; McFadden et al., 2022; DeLay et al., 2022; Cechura et al., 2021). Thus, Czech farmers could follow the German model, where technological advancements in input-saving precision farming have been the key driver of TFP growth (Von Hobe et al., 2021).

Moreover, emerging technological and biological advances offer additional opportunities to mitigate potential agricultural output losses. These include artificial intelligence and data analytics (Kariyanna and Sowjanya, 2024), gene silencing and editing for improved crop resilience (Liang et al., 2023; Bisht et al., 2019), biopesticides and biofertilizers (Kumar et al., 2022), and nanofertilizers (Kannan et al., 2023). These innovations suggest promising pathways for maintaining agricultural productivity while reducing chemical inputs. Furthermore, these technologies demonstrate significant potential to improve agricultural resilience in the face of climate variability and extreme weather events (Konfo et al., 2024; Benitez-Alfonso et al., 2023).

Reducing the dependence of European agriculture on pesticides and fertilizers under the Farm-to-Fork strategy while maintaining the productivity and competitiveness of European agriculture will be highly dependent on innovative solutions (Malorgio and Marangon, 2021; Baráth and Fertő, 2024). Among emerging agricultural technologies, precision agriculture and biotechnology—including biofertilizers and biopesticides—are the most promising solutions (Das et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2022; Flores-Félix et al., 2021; Cechura et al., 2021). In contrast, sustainable management strategies (e.g., intercropping and cover crops, organic fertilizers, and biological control agents) do not achieve productivity comparable to conventional systems that are based on chemical inputs (Martín-García et al., 2023; Boschiero et al., 2023; Triantafyllidis et al., 2023).

6.1. Policy implications

The large-scale adoption of promising agricultural technologies is likely to face significant challenges without political support. There are two key factors that require policy intervention: (i) the high initial costs and complexity of precision farming technologies, which present substantial financial and technical barriers for many farmers (Petrović et al., 2024; Nowak, 2021), and (ii) consumer concerns about biotechnology in food production, which can hinder widespread adoption (Woźniak et al., 2021). These challenges draw attention to

the importance of well-designed policies that incentivize the transition toward sustainable and resilient agricultural systems. Policy interventions must comprehensively address knowledge dissemination among farmers and consumers and technological and financial accessibility for agricultural producers.

The successful adoption of new technologies will depend heavily on farmers understanding their benefits. Therefore, fostering effective information exchange between researchers, farmers, and consumers is essential to promote informed decision making, encourage technology integration, and address psychological barriers to adoption (Gerli et al., 2022). Knowledge transfer occurs through a variety of channels, including formal education and extension services as well as experiential learning and peer observation. While formal training is crucial for raising awareness and transferring skills, it is often insufficient to overcome psychological resistance to new technologies (Lemay and Boggs, 2024; Dibbern et al., 2024; Gerli et al., 2022). Informal sources, such as peer observation, play a pivotal role in shaping positive perceptions and fostering trust toward promising technologies (Wang et al., 2023). Equally important is addressing the public perception of new agricultural technologies. Transparent and clear communication on technological advances is essential to mitigate consumer concerns, particularly on biotechnology in food production (Tyczewska et al., 2023). In addition, engaging in proactive science-based dialog that acknowledges both potential benefits and legitimate public concerns can help bridge the trust gap and foster a more informed public understanding of these innovative technologies (Lang, 2013).

Although knowledge transfer is crucial for the successful adoption of new technologies, economic incentives and public subsidies remain essential to overcome the substantial initial investment required to implement technological advancements, such as precision agriculture, particularly for small and medium-sized farms (Barnes et al., 2019; Gerli et al., 2022). In contrast, providing such subsidies to large agricultural enterprises may lack a clear rationale for market failure (Nilsson, 2017). For instance, the Czech Republic offers investment subsidies to support the adoption of precision agriculture technologies, with young farmers and organic farmers receiving priority. In addition, state-subsidized interest rates and loans with subsidies in the form of credit reductions complement these financial measures. In addition, eco-schemes such as the ‘precision agriculture’ intervention are guided by satellite data to optimize input use, reduce nutrient losses and maintain production intensity. These payments are calculated per eligible hectare, based on additional operational costs and estimated fertilizer savings—with an average saving of 5% for key crops (wheat, barley, and rapeseed). The combination of project-based and area-based support increases the availability of precision agriculture technologies for small farms (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, 2023a). A similar measure is also being considered for the use of precision technologies in plant protection product applications.

To encourage technology adoption, policymakers could strengthen support for precision agriculture by prioritizing organizational tools that encourage collaboration and resource sharing (Biro et al., 2016). For example, the establishment of agricultural clusters can connect farmers, enabling them to achieve economies of scale in accessing and utilizing advanced technologies. Additionally, technology-sharing platforms could be established to coordinate the use and maintenance of equipment through digital systems. These platforms would allow multiple farmers to share expensive machinery, significantly reducing

financial strain while optimizing equipment use. Such approaches are especially advantageous for small and medium-sized farms, where independent acquisition of precision technologies may not be economically viable.

7. Conclusions

The ongoing European transition to a more sustainable and resilient agri-food system presents significant agronomic and socioeconomic challenges. Farmers face the complicated task of adapting their production practices to comply with emerging environmental regulations while remaining competitive. Policymakers should calibrate policy instruments to achieve measurable 2030 targets to reduce pesticide and fertilizer use. At the same time, they must protect food security by maintaining or increasing agricultural productivity and increasing the global competitiveness of EU agri-food suppliers.

Using data from the Czech Republic and employing a proxy variable approach to address endogeneity within a flexible translog production function, this study assessed the effect of reducing fertilizers and pesticides on both output and TFP growth among cereal producers. The proposed methodology enhances the existing proxy variable approach to productivity estimation by integrating a flexible representation of the production process, resulting in more accurate and unbiased estimates. The empirical application of this methodology yields robust and significant results, providing novel insights into the role of variable inputs (especially fertilizers and pesticides) in output growth and TFP growth. These findings have important implications for evidence-based policy formulation, particularly in balancing agricultural productivity with sustainability objectives.

Our empirical analysis yielded several key findings. First, productivity changes were identified as the primary driver of both output and TFP growth during the analyzed period. Second, variable inputs and technological change also significantly influenced output and TFP dynamics, while quasi-fixed inputs did not contribute significantly to either. Third, the dynamics of variable inputs were heavily influenced by fertilizers and pesticides, reinforcing their critical role in driving output growth. Fourth, variable inputs contributed positively to output growth in the first half of the study period but had a negative effect in the latter part. In contrast, the positive contribution of technological change to both output and TFP growth became more pronounced toward the end of the period. Finally, simulations suggested that although a reduction in fertilizer and pesticide use is expected to cause a slight decline in agricultural output, this decline may be mitigated by technological advancements, such as precision agriculture and biotechnology. Nevertheless, the large-scale adoption of these technologies faces several challenges, including high initial costs, technical complexity, and consumer concerns about biotechnology. Policy intervention is crucial to addressing these barriers, combining financial incentives with effective knowledge dissemination.

The limitations of this study include: (i) the use of a multistep procedure, which is less efficient in estimating parameters compared to a one-step approach; and (ii) the inability of our approach to capture farmers' adaptation activities, particularly in contexts where significant restrictions require a longer time to be addressed.

Finally, this research can be further extended to explore the multiple-output nature of agricultural production (Färe and Primont, 1990), the damage control representation of pesticides (Shankar and Thirtle, 2005; Lichtenberg and Zilberman, 1986) and additional determinants of productivity. Incorporating these aspects would likely provide more accurate and nuanced insights into the complex relationship between pesticides, fertilizers, output, and TFP growth.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lukáš Čechura: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Subal C. Kumbhakar:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Zdeňka Žáková Kroupová:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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Appendix A. Identification

In this section, we demonstrate that all the parameters in the TL function in (2.6) can be identified using a multi-step procedure. We assume that producers maximize their short-run expected profit, given that v is unobserved, to choose the variable inputs F, H, O at the current period, t , while other inputs, $Q \in (K, A, L)$ are predetermined (chosen at time $t - 1$). The persistent productivity ω_{it} is assumed to be known to the farmer i when making decisions about variable inputs at time t .

Thus, the first order conditions (FOCs) with respect to the variable inputs $S \in (F, H, O)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} P_{it} \frac{\partial F(Q_{it}, S_{it})}{\partial S_{it}} \exp(\omega_{it}) \theta &= W_{S_{it}} \\ \Rightarrow P_{it} \frac{\partial \ln F(Q_{it}, S_{it})}{\partial \ln S_{it}} \exp(\omega_{it}) \theta &= \frac{W_{S_{it}} S_{it}}{F(Q_{it}, S_{it})} \\ &\Rightarrow \varepsilon_{S_{it}} \theta \exp(\omega_{it}) = \frac{W_{S_{it}} S_{it}}{P_{it} Y_{it}} \exp(\omega_{it} + v_{it}) \\ &\Rightarrow \varepsilon_{S_{it}} \theta = \frac{W_{S_{it}} S_{it}}{P_{it} Y_{it}} \exp(v_{it}), S \in (F, H, O) \end{aligned}$$

where W_S and P are prices of variable inputs (fertilizers, pesticides, and other materials) and output, respectively, $\theta = \mathbb{E}[\exp(v_{it})]$ and $\varepsilon_{S_{it}} = \frac{\partial f(q_{jit}, s_{rit})}{\partial s_{rit}}$. The prices are assumed to be exogenous, reflecting competitive input and output markets. We rewrite the above equation as

$$s_{S_{it}} \exp(v_{it}) = \varepsilon_{S_{it}} \theta, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\frac{W_{S_{it}} S_{it}}{P_{it} Y_{it}} = s_{S_{it}}$. Using the TL function in (2.6), gives

$$\varepsilon_{S_{it}} = \alpha_r + \sum_r \alpha_{rr'} s_{r'it} + \sum_j \delta_{jr} q_{jit}, S \in (F, H, O) \text{ and } r = f, h, o. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The share equations for our three variable inputs are $s_{F_{it}} \equiv \frac{W_{F_{it}} F_{it}}{P_{it} Y_{it}}$, $s_{H_{it}} \equiv \frac{W_{H_{it}} H_{it}}{P_{it} Y_{it}}$ and $s_{O_{it}} \equiv \frac{W_{O_{it}} O_{it}}{P_{it} Y_{it}}$, and the input elasticities of F, H and O from the translog function in (2.6) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{F_{it}} &= \alpha_1 + \alpha_{11} f_{it} + \alpha_{12} h_{it} + \alpha_{13} o_{it} + \delta_{11} k_{it} + \delta_{12} a_{it} + \delta_{13} l_{it} + \delta_{14} t_{it} \\ \varepsilon_{H_{it}} &= \alpha_2 + \alpha_{21} f_{it} + \alpha_{22} h_{it} + \alpha_{23} o_{it} + \delta_{21} k_{it} + \delta_{22} a_{it} + \delta_{23} l_{it} + \delta_{24} t_{it} \\ \varepsilon_{O_{it}} &= \alpha_3 + \alpha_{31} f_{it} + \alpha_{32} h_{it} + \alpha_{33} o_{it} + \delta_{31} k_{it} + \delta_{32} a_{it} + \delta_{33} l_{it} + \delta_{34} t_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Note that $\varepsilon_{F_{it}}$, $\varepsilon_{H_{it}}$ and $\varepsilon_{O_{it}}$ include all the parameters in β_1 .

A.0.1. Step 1

The first step identifies the β_1 parameters. To achieve this, we take logarithm of Eq. (A.1) and express it for F, H , and O as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln s_{F_{it}} &= \ln(\varepsilon_{F_{it}} \theta) - v_{it} \\ \ln s_{H_{it}} &= \ln(\varepsilon_{H_{it}} \theta) - v_{it} \\ \ln s_{O_{it}} &= \ln(\varepsilon_{O_{it}} \theta) - v_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where $s_{F_{it}}$, $s_{H_{it}}$ and $s_{O_{it}}$ are defined in (A.3). Note that ω does not appear in (A.4), therefore there is no endogeneity, even though $f =$

$\ln(F)$, $h = \ln(H)$ and $o = \ln(O)$ appear in the equations through $\varepsilon_{F_{it}}$, $\varepsilon_{H_{it}}$ and $\varepsilon_{O_{it}}$. Since ω does not appear in the above share equations, there is no need to make any additional assumption (such as invertibility of ω) about it. Endogeneity occurs only when f, h, o and ω appear together in the same equation. Therefore, (A.4) can be estimated using non-linear least squares (NLS) on an equation-by-equation basis to obtain consistent estimates of the parameters in $\varepsilon_{M_{it}}$, $\varepsilon_{H_{it}}$, and $\varepsilon_{O_{it}}$ all multiplied by θ .

The equations in (A.4) give estimate of $\beta_1 \times \theta$. To recover β_1 , we must first estimate θ from $\hat{\theta} = \mathbb{E}[\exp(\hat{v}_{it})]$ where $\hat{v}_{it} = -\ln s_{F_{it}} + \ln(\varepsilon_{F_{it}}\theta)$. We then get another estimate of θ using \hat{v}_{it} from $\hat{v}_{it} = -\ln s_{H_{it}} + \ln(\varepsilon_{H_{it}}\theta)$ and \hat{v}_{it} from $\hat{v}_{it} = -\ln s_{O_{it}} + \ln(\varepsilon_{O_{it}}\theta)$. An average of these three can be used to get a single estimate of θ . Finally, we get estimates of β_1 by dividing each of the NLS parameters in (A.4) by the estimated θ . This is when $T(\cdot; \beta_1)$ is identified.

A.0.2. Step 2

In this step, we identify the remaining parameters in β_2 . In order to accomplish this, we first express ω_{it} in terms of functions of the data and the estimated parameters from Step 1 (i.e., β_1) using the FOCs. We then assume a Markov process for ω . Using these two features, we rewrite the production function in terms of β_2 and the dynamics of ω . The details are follows:

(i) The FOC with respect to F implies

$$\begin{aligned} P_{it} \varepsilon_{F_{it}} \theta \exp(\omega_{it}) &= \frac{w_{F_{it}} F_{it}}{F(Q_{it}, F_{it})} \\ \Rightarrow \omega_{it} &= \ln\left(\frac{w_{F_{it}} F_{it}}{P_{it}}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{F_{it}}\theta) - f(q_{jit}) \\ &= \ln\left(\frac{w_{F_{it}} F_{it}}{P_{it}}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{F_{it}}\theta) - T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) - TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) \end{aligned}$$

which can be written as

$$\omega_{it} = RF(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) - TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2). \tag{A.5}$$

Note that no invertibility assumption on ω is needed here. We move ω_{it} to the left-hand side of the equation above. Similarly, the FOCs for H and O gives

$$\omega_{it} = RH(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) - TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2), \tag{A.6}$$

$$\omega_{it} = RO(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) - TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2), \tag{A.7}$$

where $RF(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) \equiv \ln\left(\frac{w_{F_{it}} F_{it}}{P_{it}}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{F_{it}}\theta) - T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$, $RH(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) \equiv \ln\left(\frac{w_{H_{it}} H_{it}}{P_{it}}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{H_{it}}\theta) - T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ and $RO(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) \equiv \ln\left(\frac{w_{O_{it}} O_{it}}{P_{it}}\right) - \ln(\varepsilon_{O_{it}}\theta) - T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ which are known/estimated since they consist of data and estimated parameters from Step 1. So $RF(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$, $RH(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ and $RO(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ can be treated as known (estimated) variables, and we denote them as RF_{it} , RH_{it} and RO_{it} .²⁴

(ii) We follow the proxy variable literature (e.g. Olley and Pakes, 1996, Levinsohn and Petrin, 2003, Ackerberg et al., 2015, Gandhi et al., 2020) and assume that persistent productivity ω_{it} follows a Markov process. The most commonly used form is the first order (AR(1)) Markov process, i.e., $\omega_{it} = \mathbb{E}(\omega_{it} | \omega_{it-1}, s_{rit}) + \eta_{it} = \rho\omega_{it-1} + \eta_{it}$ where η_{it} is a transient productivity shock

(productivity innovation) with zero mean and uncorrelated with any of the variables in the production function.²⁵

Using (A.5)

$$\omega_{it} = \rho\omega_{it-1} + \eta_{it} = \rho[RF_{it-1} - TL(k_{it-1}, a_{it-1}, l_{it-1}; \beta_2)] + \eta_{it} \tag{A.8}$$

$$= \rho RF_{it-1} - \rho TL(k_{it-1}, a_{it-1}, l_{it-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it}.$$

Similarly, using (A.6) and (A.7)

$$\omega_{it} = \rho RH_{it-1} - \rho TL(k_{it-1}, a_{it-1}, l_{it-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it}. \tag{A.9}$$

$$\omega_{it} = \rho RO_{it-1} - \rho TL(k_{it-1}, a_{it-1}, l_{it-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it}. \tag{A.10}$$

We take an average of these three to get a single ω_{it} which is

$$\omega_{it} = \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} - \rho TL(k_{it-1}, a_{it-1}, l_{it-1}; \beta_2) + \eta_{it}, \tag{A.11}$$

where $\bar{R}_{it-1} = [RF_{it-1} + RH_{it-1} + RO_{it-1}]/3$. Finally, we rewrite the translog function as

$$\begin{aligned} y_{it} - T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1) &= TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) + \rho[\bar{R}_{it-1} - TL(q_{it-1}; \beta_2)] + v_{it} + \eta_{it} \\ \Rightarrow \tilde{y}_{it} &= TL(q_{jit}; \beta_2) + \rho \bar{R}_{it-1} - \rho TL(q_{jit-1}; \beta_2) + e_{it} \end{aligned} \tag{A.12}$$

where $\tilde{y}_{it} \equiv y_{it} - T(s_{rit}, q_{jit}; \beta_1)$ and $e_{it} = v_{it} + \eta_{it}$. Note that, $\bar{R}_{it-1} - TL(q_{it-1}; \beta_2)$ comes from taking a lag of (A.10). One can then use NLS to (A.12) to estimate ρ and β_2 parameters. Note that ρ is the coefficient of \bar{R}_{it-1} which identifies ρ and $\rho TL(q_{it-1}; \beta_2) = TL(q_{it-1}; \rho \beta_2)$ identifies β_2 .²⁶ Therefore, Steps 1 and 2 together identify both β_1 and β_2 which are the parameters of the production function in (2.6), except for the farm effects μ_i . Productivity ω_{it} can then be obtained by averaging ω_{it} from (A.5), (A.6) and (A.7).

Appendix B

See Fig. B.1 and Tables B.1–B.9.

Table B.1

FADN code for employed variables.

Variable	FADN code
Fertilizers	SE295
Pesticides	SE300
Total specific costs	SE281
Total agricultural overhead	SE336
Utilized agricultural area	SE025
Total current assets	SE465
Total labor input	SE010
Cereal production	SE140
Total crop production	SE135
Cows' milk and milk products	SE216
Total output livestock and livestock production	SE206
Other output	SE256

Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this paper are available from the Farm Accountancy Data Network – Czech Republic. However, access to these data is restricted as they were used under license for this study. Data can be obtained from the authors with permission from the Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information.

²⁴ Note that there are three equations for ω_{it} , because there is a single ω but three variable inputs. This means ω can be obtained from any one of them or by taking an average of the three. Introduction of allocative errors will not change this, except that (A.5), (A.6) and (A.7) will include these allocative errors.

²⁵ Having determinants of ω helps in identification because it provides independent variations other than the inputs. However, the model is identified without determinant variables such as subsidy, R&D, FDI, and similar variables.

²⁶ The presence of persistent productivity ω can be tested from the statistical significance of its estimate.

Fig. B.1. Productivity change.

Table B.2
Estimation of alternative models.

Model 1: 3 variable(f,h,o), 3 quasi-fixed inputs(l,a,k)					Model 2: 2 variable(fh,o), 3 quasi-fixed inputs (l,a,k)					Model 3: 4 variable(f,h,o,l), 2 quasi-fixed inputs(a,k)					Model 4: 3 variable(fh,o,l), 2 quasi-fixed inputs(a,k)				
Variable	Coef.	Std.Error	p-value	R.Coeff.	Variable	Coef.	Std.Error	p-value	R.Coeff.	Variable	Coef.	Std.Error	p-value	R.Coeff.	Variable	Coef.	Std.Error	p-value	R.Coeff.
f	0.086	0.000	0.000	0.081	fh	0.160	0.001	0.000	0.150	f	0.086	0.000	0.000	0.080	fh	0.160	0.001	0.000	0.147
h	0.076	0.000	0.000	0.072	o	0.649	0.002	0.000	0.609	h	0.076	0.000	0.000	0.070	o	0.649	0.002	0.000	0.596
o	0.646	0.002	0.000	0.608	l	0.091	0.016	0.000	0.093	o	0.646	0.002	0.000	0.596	l	0.091	0.016	0.000	0.084
l	0.093	0.016	0.000	0.084	a	0.168	0.023	0.000	0.173	l	0.092	0.001	0.000	0.084	a	0.178	0.021	0.000	0.178
a	0.162	0.022	0.000	0.155	k	0.100	0.009	0.000	0.094	a	0.173	0.021	0.000	0.173	k	0.093	0.009	0.000	0.093
k	0.098	0.009	0.000	0.098	t	0.000	0.001	0.686	k	0.094	0.009	0.000	0.094	t	0.000	0.001	0.550	0.000	
t	0.001	0.001	0.214	0.000	fh ²	0.027	0.000	0.000	0.025	t	0.000	0.001	0.550	0.000	fh ²	0.027	0.000	0.000	0.025
f ²	0.017	0.000	0.000	0.016	o ²	0.235	0.005	0.000	0.221	f ²	0.017	0.000	0.000	0.015	o ²	0.235	0.005	0.000	0.216
h ²	0.016	0.000	0.000	0.015	l ²	0.083	0.025	0.001	0.083	h ²	0.016	0.000	0.000	0.014	l ²	0.083	0.025	0.000	0.021
o ²	0.236	0.005	0.000	0.222	a ²	0.034	0.022	0.121	0.034	o ²	0.236	0.005	0.000	0.217	a ²	-0.036	0.013	0.007	-0.036
l ²	0.079	0.025	0.001	0.079	k ²	0.067	0.009	0.000	0.067	l ²	0.022	0.001	0.000	0.020	k ²	0.084	0.007	0.000	0.084
a ²	-0.005	0.022	0.811	-0.005	t ²	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	a ²	-0.036	0.013	0.007	-0.036	t ²	0.004	0.000	0.000	0.004
k ²	0.067	0.009	0.000	0.067	fhx	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	k ²	0.084	0.007	0.000	0.084	fhx	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005
t ²	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	fxo	-0.032	0.001	0.000	-0.030	t ²	0.004	0.000	0.000	0.004	fxo	-0.032	0.001	0.000	-0.030
fxh	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	fxa	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.021	fxh	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	fxa	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.021
fxo	-0.032	0.001	0.000	-0.030	fxl	-0.010	0.001	0.000	-0.009	fxo	-0.032	0.001	0.000	-0.030	fxl	-0.010	0.001	0.000	-0.009
fxa	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.021	fxk	-0.002	0.001	0.001	-0.002	fxa	0.023	0.000	0.000	0.021	fxk	-0.002	0.001	0.001	-0.002
fxl	-0.010	0.001	0.000	-0.009	fxf	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	fxl	-0.010	0.001	0.000	-0.009	fxf	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005
fxk	-0.002	0.001	0.001	-0.002	hxo	-0.017	0.001	0.000	-0.016	fxk	-0.002	0.001	0.001	-0.002	hxo	-0.017	0.001	0.000	-0.016
fxf	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	hxa	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.012	fxf	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.005	hxa	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.012
hxo	-0.017	0.001	0.000	-0.016	hxl	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.008	hxo	-0.017	0.001	0.000	-0.016	hxl	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.008
hxa	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.012	hxk	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.007	hxa	0.013	0.001	0.000	0.012	hxk	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.007
hxl	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.008	oxf	-0.062	0.004	0.000	-0.059	hxl	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.008	oxf	-0.062	0.004	0.000	-0.059
hxk	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.007	oxh	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037	hxk	-0.008	0.000	0.000	-0.007	oxh	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037
oxf	-0.062	0.004	0.000	-0.059	oxa	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002	oxf	-0.062	0.004	0.000	-0.058	oxa	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002
oxh	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037	oxl	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.081	oxh	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037	oxl	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.080
oxa	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002	oxk	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.050	oxa	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002	oxk	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.049
oxl	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.082	lxa	-0.021	0.020	0.300	oxl	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.080	lxa	-0.021	0.020	0.300	-0.019	
oxk	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.050	lxk	0.039	0.013	0.002	oxk	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.049	lxk	0.039	0.013	0.002	0.037	
fhxo	0.001	0.001	0.541	0.001	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	fhxo	0.001	0.001	0.541	0.001	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
fhxa	0.013	0.002	0.000	0.013	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	fhxa	0.013	0.002	0.000	0.013	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
fhxl	-0.036	0.002	0.000	-0.033	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	fhxl	-0.036	0.002	0.000	-0.033	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
fhxk	-0.011	0.001	0.000	-0.010	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	fhxk	-0.011	0.001	0.000	-0.010	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
oxfx	-0.105	0.003	0.000	-0.099	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	oxfx	-0.105	0.003	0.000	-0.099	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
oxhx	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	oxhx	-0.040	0.004	0.000	-0.037	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
oxax	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	oxax	0.003	0.005	0.635	0.002	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
oxlx	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.082	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	oxlx	-0.087	0.004	0.000	-0.080	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
oxkx	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.050	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	oxkx	-0.054	0.003	0.000	-0.049	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
lxa	-0.021	0.020	0.300	-0.019	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	lxa	-0.021	0.020	0.300	-0.019	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
lxk	0.039	0.013	0.002	0.037	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	lxk	0.039	0.013	0.002	0.037	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
axk	-0.037	0.010	0.000	-0.033	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	axk	-0.037	0.010	0.000	-0.033	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
fxl	-0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.001	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	fxl	-0.001	0.000	0.000	-0.001	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
fxh	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	fxh	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
oxl	-0.004	0.000	0.000	-0.004	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	oxl	-0.004	0.000	0.000	-0.004	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
lxt	0.001	0.002	0.499	0.000	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	lxt	0.001	0.002	0.499	0.000	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
axt	0.010	0.002	0.000	0.000	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	axt	0.010	0.002	0.000	0.000	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
kxt	-0.002	0.001	0.049	0.000	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	kxt	-0.002	0.001	0.049	0.000	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
q _h	-0.137	0.025	0.000	-0.147	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	q _h	-0.137	0.025	0.000	-0.147	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
q _l	0.018	0.021	0.390	0.017	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	q _l	0.018	0.021	0.390	0.017	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
q _a	0.011	0.014	0.412	0.015	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	q _a	0.011	0.014	0.412	0.015	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	
q _o	0.007	0.002	0.004	0.006	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	q _o	0.007	0.002	0.004	0.006	lxk	0.043	0.013	0.001	0.041	
const.	-0.074	0.029	0.010	-0.063	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	const.	-0.074	0.029	0.010	-0.063	lxa	-0.022	0.020	0.271	-0.018	

Table B.3
Differences in parameter estimates — t-test.

Production input	Differences in parameter estimates			t-test statistic			p-value		
	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>f</i>		0.000			0.000			1.000	
<i>h</i>	0.002	0.000	0.002	1.535	0.000	1.535	0.125	1.000	0.125
<i>o</i>	-0.003	0.000	-0.003	-0.879	0.000	-0.879	0.379	1.000	0.379
<i>l</i>	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.068	0.068	0.105	0.946	0.945	0.916
<i>a</i>	-0.006	-0.011	-0.016	-0.125	-0.249	-0.369	0.900	0.804	0.712
<i>k</i>	-0.002	0.005	0.005	-0.080	0.265	0.285	0.936	0.791	0.776

Note: Model 2 and model 4 aggregate fertilizer and pesticides into one variable (agrochemical inputs).

Table B.4
Differences in productivity change and their tests.

Models	Difference	t-test	p-value
1vs2	-0.004	-1.347	0.178
1vs3	0.002	0.958	0.338
1vs4	0.000	-0.200	0.842

Table B.5
Correlation coefficients and their p-values.

Innovation in productivity in time <i>t</i>	<i>a</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>l</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>k</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>h</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>f</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}	<i>o</i> _{<i>t</i>-1}
Correlation coefficient	-0.0010	-0.0005	-0.0098	0.0110	0.0071	-0.0102
p-value	0.9413	0.9686	0.4479	0.3953	0.5833	0.4297
Innovation in productivity in time <i>t</i>	<i>a</i> _{<i>t</i>}	<i>l</i> _{<i>t</i>}	<i>k</i> _{<i>t</i>}	<i>h</i> _{<i>t</i>}	<i>f</i> _{<i>t</i>}	<i>o</i> _{<i>t</i>}
Correlation coefficient	0.0002	0.0002	-0.0001	0.0084	-0.0021	-0.0196
p-value	0.9861	0.9905	0.9925	0.5144	0.8693	0.1302

Table B.6
Output dynamics and decomposition.

Year	Output growth		Variable Inputs change		Quasi-fixed Inputs change		TC		Productivity change	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
2010	-0.1506	0.2068	-0.0017	0.0942	-0.0005	0.0841	-0.0063	0.1408	-0.1349	0.0963
2011	-0.0399	0.2786	0.0281	0.1100	0.0084	0.0821	0.0032	0.1443	-0.0859	0.1172
2012	0.0437	0.2251	0.0067	0.0898	0.0021	0.0870	-0.0022	0.1484	0.0256	0.1076
2013	0.0376	0.2000	0.0148	0.0726	0.0095	0.0678	0.0030	0.1475	0.0063	0.0779
2014	0.0940	0.2025	0.0275	0.0768	0.0099	0.0791	0.0103	0.1494	0.0451	0.0773
2015	0.1368	0.1763	-0.0084	0.0732	0.0044	0.0832	0.0091	0.1456	0.1269	0.0769
2016	0.0746	0.1893	0.0087	0.0704	0.0164	0.1438	0.0078	0.1464	0.0364	0.0728
2017	-0.0925	0.1733	0.0018	0.0657	0.0002	0.0776	0.0246	0.1446	-0.1131	0.0694
2018	0.0203	0.1847	-0.0036	0.0833	0.0072	0.0772	0.0350	0.1449	-0.0211	0.0927
2019	0.0167	0.1897	0.0049	0.0727	0.0052	0.0897	0.0326	0.1468	-0.0322	0.0849
2020	0.0495	0.1859	0.0103	0.0732	-0.0040	0.0815	0.0371	0.1480	-0.0017	0.0687

Note: TC denotes technological change.

Table B.7
TFP dynamics and decomposition.

Year	TFP growth		Variable Inputs change		Quasi-fixed Inputs change		TC		Productivity change	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
2010	-0.197	0.254	-0.047	0.191	-0.001	0.084	-0.006	0.141	-0.135	0.096
2011	-0.126	0.303	-0.050	0.212	0.008	0.082	0.003	0.144	-0.086	0.117
2012	-0.015	0.250	-0.058	0.220	0.002	0.087	-0.002	0.148	0.026	0.108
2013	0.028	0.227	0.003	0.158	0.009	0.068	0.003	0.148	0.006	0.078
2014	0.051	0.215	-0.013	0.143	0.010	0.079	0.010	0.149	0.045	0.077
2015	0.181	0.206	0.031	0.134	0.004	0.083	0.009	0.146	0.127	0.077
2016	0.068	0.205	0.001	0.145	0.016	0.144	0.008	0.146	0.036	0.073
2017	-0.105	0.188	-0.012	0.097	0.000	0.078	0.025	0.145	-0.113	0.069
2018	0.022	0.195	-0.002	0.105	0.007	0.077	0.035	0.145	-0.021	0.093
2019	0.025	0.184	0.012	0.087	0.005	0.090	0.033	0.147	-0.032	0.085
2020	0.029	0.183	-0.010	0.081	-0.004	0.082	0.037	0.148	-0.002	0.069

Note: TC denotes technological change.

Table B.8
Weighted productivity and decomposition.

Year	W. prod.	Unw. prod.	Covariance	W. prod. ch.	Unw. prod. ch.	Covariance ch.
2009	1.979	1.984	-0.005			
2010	1.820	1.847	-0.027	-0.159	-0.137	-0.022
2011	1.745	1.762	-0.017	-0.075	-0.085	0.010
2012	1.749	1.779	-0.030	0.004	0.017	-0.013
2013	1.758	1.776	-0.019	0.008	-0.003	0.011
2014	1.794	1.811	-0.017	0.036	0.034	0.002
2015	1.927	1.939	-0.012	0.133	0.129	0.005
2016	1.939	1.970	-0.031	0.011	0.030	-0.019
2017	1.799	1.849	-0.050	-0.140	-0.120	-0.019
2018	1.773	1.831	-0.058	-0.026	-0.019	-0.008
2019	1.758	1.803	-0.045	-0.015	-0.028	0.013
2020	1.735	1.785	-0.050	-0.023	-0.018	-0.005

Note: W denotes weighted; Unw denotes unweighted; prod. denotes productivity; prod. ch. denotes productivity change; ch. denotes change.

Table B.9
Decomposition of variable inputs dynamics.

Year	Variable Input growth		C. Fertilizer		C. Pesticides		C. other materials	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
2010	-0.002	0.094	-0.003	0.042	0.007	0.022	-0.006	0.084
2011	0.028	0.110	0.013	0.046	0.011	0.024	0.004	0.094
2012	0.007	0.090	0.007	0.034	0.005	0.025	-0.005	0.081
2013	0.015	0.073	0.007	0.030	0.002	0.020	0.005	0.063
2014	0.027	0.077	0.000	0.026	0.001	0.016	0.026	0.069
2015	-0.008	0.073	0.005	0.028	-0.001	0.018	-0.013	0.065
2016	0.009	0.070	0.007	0.026	-0.001	0.016	0.003	0.062
2017	0.002	0.066	-0.003	0.030	0.000	0.015	0.005	0.053
2018	-0.004	0.083	-0.003	0.024	-0.002	0.017	0.002	0.076
2019	0.005	0.073	0.000	0.024	-0.002	0.015	0.007	0.063
2020	0.010	0.073	0.001	0.022	-0.003	0.018	0.012	0.063

Note: C denotes contribution.

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